

More-than-human Design (MTHD): Reimagining Urban Spaces for Tyne Kittiwakes

Abstract

This article examines More-than-human Design (MTHD) through the case of Tyne Kittiwakes - the world's most inland breeding colonies, located in Newcastle and Gateshead, UK (Coulson, 2011, p.255). Drawing on posthuman theory (Forlano, 2017; Haraway, 2016; Tsing, 2021; Wakkary, 2021), it challenges anthropocentric urban design by exploring interspecies approaches in three participatory workshops at the BALTIC Centre for Contemporary Art. The workshops engaged 121 participants, including architects, artists, ornithologists, and residents to reimagine urban futures, recognising kittiwakes as active agents rather than management problems. Using a temporal layering methodology, participants shifted from viewing the birds as urban disruptions to cultivating "ecological empathy". The study traces past socio-ecological formations, interrogates present conflicts, and envisions symbiotic futures. Despite challenges such as regulatory barriers and professional resistance, the findings demonstrate how MTHD can reposition cities as inclusive multispecies habitats and propose three core principles for contextually grounded practice.

Keywords

More-than-human design (MTHD), Ecological empathy, Tyne kittiwakes, Interspecies thinking, Participatory workshops

Adscription to Becoming

This research demonstrates how architectural and urban practice can move beyond anthropocentric paradigms toward interspecies collaboration. The Tyne Kittiwakes case illustrates architecture's role in navigating planetary cohabitation during climate disruption, as these seabirds' inland migration signals broader environmental transitions demanding new urban ecological relationships. The study aligns with the congress's emphasis on "speculative, qualitative inquiries" through experimental and participatory workshops. Rather than treating kittiwakes as management subjects, the research positions them as active design collaborators, advancing speculative futures where buildings and urban infrastructure operate within ecological cycles transcending human temporalities. The emergent concept of "temporal zoning" - seasonal restrictions prioritising avian reproductive success - illustrates architecture's transition from spatial control to interspecies time-sharing facilitation. This work advances the congress's transitional architecture agenda by proposing three MTHD principles: cyclical responsiveness, situated collaboration, and experimental humility. Together, these reframe design as the cultivation of multispecies flourishing rather than the management of nonhuman life. The research further suggests pathways for transforming architectural education and practice, shifting emphasis from object production to the facilitation of interspecies relations. Such evolution reflects a necessary adaptation for addressing Anthropocene realities and planetary transitions, directly responding to the congress's call for architectures attuned to our changing planet.

Essay text:

Introduction

Along the River Tyne in Newcastle and Gateshead, UK, an extraordinary phenomenon unfolds each spring: thousands of Black-legged Kittiwakes (*Rissa tridactyla*) arrive not at their traditional coastal cliffs, but at concrete ledges, bridge structures, and building facades deep within the urban core, with some nesting as far as 17 kilometres inland from the sea (Turner, 2010). This remarkable adaptation marks the world's most inland-nesting kittiwake population. Their presence reflects warming seas (Carroll, 2015, Descamps, 2017), rising storminess and cyclonic conditions (Clairbaux, 2021), and wider environmental disruptions that undermine breeding success on natural coasts (Mitchell, 2020), forcing the species to seek new forms of coexistence within human-made landscapes.

Cities host countless nonhuman species, yet their presence is largely mediated by human decision-making. Urban and architectural spaces are primarily designed to optimise conditions for people, while the needs and impacts on other-than-human beings are often overlooked or considered secondary as peripheral or externalities (Arcari, 2018, p.78). Such anthropocentrism has contributed to biodiversity loss, habitat fragmentation, and wider ecological disruption (Müller et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2013). The persistence of urban seabirds such as the Tyne Kittiwakes highlights the inadequacy of conventional planning paradigms and calls for approaches that enable cohabitation rather than exclusion. The emerging field of More-than-Human Design (MTHD) addresses the critical challenge of designing urban and architectural interventions that serve both human and non-human species (Demir & Coşkun, 2025). By engaging diverse stakeholders, including non-human actors, MTHD steps beyond anthropocentric perspectives, decentres human privilege, and approaches urban systems through a more holistic, ecological understanding (Forlano, 2017). As Haraway (2008, p.3) argues, “sharing our bodies with these others means that the experience of being human is always intertwined with the existence of other species”. This recognition of fundamental interdependence challenges designers to work within what Wakkary (2021) calls “networks of things”, where both human and nonhuman actors interact with varying forms of agency, influence, and dependency.

As Anne Galloway observes, “Complementary ways of thinking, doing, and making emphasise the practice of care and imagination - and the challenge is to work with, not against, vulnerability, humility and interdependence” (Superflux, 2021). This project is part of the Navigating Urban Ecologies (NUE) project funded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council in the UK. It develops a bottom-up application of MTHD through workshops and discussions held at the BALTIC Centre for Contemporary Art (BALTIC), which gathered architects, urban designers, ornithologists, ecologists, and community members to operationalise MTHD principles for Tyne Kittiwakes. Rather than treating these seabirds as management challenges or nuisances, the project positions them as active collaborators in envisioning urban futures. With three participatory workshops spanning from May to July 2025, it explores how interspecies ethics of care, adaptability, and cohabitation can transform both the physical environments and the conceptual frameworks that underpin urban and architectural design.

By documenting and analysing our experimental workshops, this research investigates what it means to engage kittiwakes and nature in design through a more-than-human posthumanist lens (Ulmer, 2017), while beginning to map best practices and methodological approaches in nature-centred design and research. The findings show how MTHD can reconfigure cities from spaces of exclusion and control into inclusive habitats founded on entanglement, reciprocity, and cohabitation. This work positions architecture as a pivotal medium for navigating the interspecies thinking of the Anthropocene, showing that urban environments can become generative sites for interspecies collaboration. These workshops produced patches of liveability where humans and non-humans thrive together, revealing pathways toward more resilient, ecologically vibrant, and socially inclusive urban futures.

Theoretical Framework: More-than-Human Design

The more-than-human design (MTHD) approach recognises that human existence is fundamentally intertwined with nonhuman life. This biological and ecological entanglement necessitates a design approach that moves beyond anthropocentrism toward what design studio Superflux describes as remembering “we are not just on this Earth: we are of this Earth. The interdependence is real: humanity as ecology, ecology as humanity” (2021). Unlike conventional ecological design approaches that often treat nature as a resource to be managed or a backdrop for human activity, MTHD positions nonhuman actors as active participants with their own forms of intelligence, agency, and creativity. This underscores a shift from extractionist relationships toward what Forlano (2017) calls new relations that allow for “justice and equality for humans and nonhumans”. Rather than designing solutions for ecological problems, MTHD involves designing with ecological systems, attending to “the experience and agency of the nonhumans in ecology” (Wakkary, 2021).

Current MTHD practices can be broadly categorised into three approaches: the political and systematic, which focuses on representation of nonhuman actors, such as the project Embassy of the North Sea (2025); the relational, which explores connections between human and nonhuman entities (like HUB Ocean “Becoming an ocean carer” (HUB Ocean, 2025); and the experimental, which materialises new forms of collaboration in real contexts. Contemporary practitioners like Terreform One (2025) explore cyclical ecological existence in designs that acknowledge ever-changing biological systems, while Space 10 (2023) investigates regenerative futures that challenge extractionist production models. Studio Ossidiana takes a particularly radical approach, creating projects

like “Birds' Palace” (2021) and “NDSM Lusthof” (2024) in Amsterdam, both of which position humans as observers rather than controllers (Studio Ossidiana, 2025). Urban Reef presents experimental materialisations of caring attitudes toward nonhuman ecology through structures designed specifically for multispecies habitation.

Analysis of these projects uncovers several distinguishing characteristics of MTHD practice. First, these projects are inherently speculative, driven by poetic expressions of questions about possible futures rather than definitive solutions. They create what Dunne and Raby (2013) call “design friction”, highlighting tensions between extractionist human behaviour and alternative relationships based on care and reciprocity. Second, MTHD projects embrace temporality differently than conventional design, acknowledging that ecological existence is cyclical and ever-changing. Third, these projects prioritise different forms of human positioning, from Urban Reef's inclusive multispecies spaces to Studio Ossidiana's observer-human paradigm, each exploring alternative ways humans might inhabit ecological systems. However, current MTHD practice faces several limitations identified by this analysis. Many projects remain detached from their immediate contexts, emerging less from ongoing multispecies interactions within local ecosystems than from abstract experimentation. Others neglect cyclical temporalities, or “nonhuman time”, thereby overlooking critical dimensions of ecological adaptation and change.

Workshop Methodology and Process

Along the River Tyne between Newcastle and Gateshead, the kittiwakes have demonstrated remarkable adaptability to urban infrastructure, colonising concrete ledges, bridge supports, and building facades that mimic the cliff faces of their ancestral habitats (Turner, 2010; Coulson, 2011). However, their urban occupation creates significant conflicts with human inhabitants and city management systems. The birds' nesting activities generate noise, mess, and maintenance challenges for building owners (Coulson, 2011; Rock, 2016; Turner, 2019), while seasonal influxes disrupt the conventional use of riverside buildings and infrastructure. Additionally, urban hazards such as deterrent measures, artificial lighting, and limited food sources present ongoing survival challenges that differ markedly from their coastal counterparts. Despite these conflicts, the kittiwakes have acquired profound cultural significance within Newcastle and Gateshead communities. Local residents have developed emotional attachments to these ‘urban colonisers’, viewing them as symbols of resilience and wildness within the cityscape (Heavisides, 2020; Kurikka, 2023). They have become cultural and emotional co-residents rather than merely ecological inhabitants, embedded in local identity and urban narratives.

Recognising the complex relationships between the Tyne Kittiwakes and the communities of Newcastle and Gateshead, this research employed a participatory methodology designed to explore MTHD principles with direct engagement with local stakeholders. Three MTHD workshops were conducted on 16 May, 30 May, and 25 July 2025, strategically timed to span the kittiwakes' breeding season and allow participants to observe the birds' behavioural patterns, nesting activities, and seasonal presence along the River Tyne. Each workshop brought together approximately 35-45 participants representing diverse perspectives on urban cohabitation, including architects, urban designers, artists, ornithologists, ecologists, local residents, building managers, and community activists. This interdisciplinary composition was essential for capturing the multiple ways humans encounter and interpret kittiwake presence. The workshops were held at BALTIC, the venue's riverside location provided direct access to major kittiwake colonies and its fourth-floor terrace offered dedicated observation of these birds. The workshops took place in BALTIC's Front Room, a space frequently used for public engagement. Its adjoining terrace, overlooking the River Tyne, provided panoramic views of the kittiwake colonies while offering a neutral setting for dialogue among stakeholders. Recruitment was conducted through Eventbrite and BALTIC's publicity channels, with Northumbria architecture students specifically invited to Workshop 2. All participants received an information sheet and verbal briefing before providing written informed consent. Ethical approval was granted by Northumbria University (Ref. #10253).

The three-workshop sequence was designed progressively, integrating arts-led approaches with architectural thinking. The 1st workshop (16 May, Figure 1) coincided with nest building and egg laying and employed an arts-led methodology that allowed participants to observe the birds' site selection and territorial behaviours while using artistic expression to document the site as it currently exists and to explore how creative ideas could be embedded within urban and architectural contexts. The 2nd workshop (30 May, Figure 2) took place during the peak breeding season, when human-kittiwake conflicts are most apparent and focused on architectural interventions and spatial design solutions. The 3rd and final workshop (25 July, Figure 3) fostered a more mature dialogue that integrated both arts and

architecture perspectives, aiming for more developed and integrated ideas aligned with the whole kittiwake breeding season. This timing enabled reflection on the complete breeding cycle and post-breeding urban dynamics, encouraging participants to consider the full temporal complexity of human-kittiwake cohabitation.

Figure 1: Workshop 1 - Exploring Urban Ecology through Art

Central to our methodology was the challenge of incorporating kittiwake perspectives into design processes without anthropomorphising or speaking for the birds. To foster multispecies empathy, we combined observational and analytical techniques that grounded speculation in careful attention to actual bird behaviours and ecological relationships. Workshops encouraged participants to begin with direct fieldwork along riverside colonies and on the kittiwake terrace of BALTIC, where participants documented kittiwake behaviours and interactions with urban structures. Our professional ornithologist, Daniel Turner who brings over 30 years of experience in kittiwake surveys, led the lectures and discussions, guiding participants in interpreting bird behaviours and understanding their ecological needs. Role-reversal exercises using arts and architectural explorations asked participants to navigate urban space from a bird's perspective, considering wind, height, and landing approaches in nest site selection. Sensory mapping extended this perspective to non-visual dimensions, such as calls marking territory and seasonal food availability. Collaborative mapping on large-scale river charts layered kittiwake territories, flight paths, and potential conflict zones against human activities and infrastructure, revealing overlaps often hidden in conventional planning.

Workshop activities were systematically documented through multiple methods to capture both explicit discussions and tacit knowledge generation. Data collection included audio and video recordings of verbal exchanges and debates, time-lapse photography of collaborative mapping and design processes, participants' individual notes and sketches, and post-workshop surveys documenting evolving perspectives. Analysis proceeded iteratively, with preliminary findings from each workshop informing the design of subsequent sessions. Audio transcripts underwent thematic coding to identify recurring concerns, emerging design proposals, and shifts in participants' understanding of human-kittiwake relationships. Visual materials like sketches, maps, and photographs were analysed for spatial patterns and design innovations, while transcripts revealed conceptual developments and areas of consensus or disagreement among stakeholders.

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Photo Resource:
New kittiwake hotel in
front of the Kunstforening
Wild Lab Project

Designing for Coexistence -The Kittiwake Hotel

Front Room,
Baltic Centre for Contemporary Art

30 05 2025, Friday, 12 - 16 PM

Figure 2: Workshop 2 - Designing for Coexistence – The Kittiwake Hotel

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BALTIC

Exploring Urban Ecology through Art & Architecture

Front Room,
Baltic Centre for Contemporary Art

25 07 2025, Friday, 12 - 16 PM

Figure 3: Workshop 3 - Exploring Urban Ecology through Art & Architecture

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Discussion on MTHD

The workshops showed unexpectedly high levels of participant enthusiasm and affective engagement with kittiwake welfare beyond the anticipated scope. Post-workshop surveys indicated that 79% of participants described developing “personal connections” to kittiwakes they had observed over the years, with many sharing detailed stories about specific birds and expressing profound emotional responses to witnessing nesting behaviours, territorial negotiations, and parent-chick interactions. Long-term Newcastle residents, in particular, recalled observing the development of local colonies over time, describing how initial irritation had gradually shifted to a sense of protective concern. One participant noted: *“I never realised they were so intelligent - watching them solve problems about where to build and how to build made me see them as neighbours rather than nuisances... They bring life to the city, and I simply hope to welcome their return each year.”*

Community members consistently expressed strong protective attitudes towards the colonies. Multiple participants raised unsolicited concerns about disturbance and the risks posed by deterrent measures that create unsafe conditions for nesting birds. Several residents even described actively intervening to prevent vandalism or harassment of nesting sites. This protective stance was also evident within the design discussions, where participants were concerned about lighting placement or maintenance scheduling that could disrupt breeding activities. In these moments, participants assumed the role of informal advocates for kittiwake welfare, ensuring that ecological requirements were prioritised over human convenience.

Workshop participants generated targeted spatial interventions that explicitly prioritised kittiwake ecological requirements while integrating compatible human activities. Design proposals, such as a modified Tyne Bridge support, incorporating ledge extensions, wind barriers, and drainage systems that replicate the microclimatic conditions of natural cliff faces, thereby creating high-quality nesting habitats capable of sustaining larger and more stable kittiwake colonies (Figure 4 & 5). Using the iterative collaboration with the ornithologist, some interventions transcended minimal compliance, actively enhancing breeding success and chick survival rates. Concurrently, a riverside walkway design by an architectural student proposed elevated observation platforms strategically positioned along kittiwake flight corridors, balancing human engagement with the preservation of critical bird territories (Figure 6). This intervention shows a sophisticated understanding of kittiwake spatial behaviour, incorporating 50-meter buffer zones around active colonies and sight-line calculations to minimise visual disturbance.

Figure 4: Sketches of Kittiwake Hotels by a Participant

Figure 5: Physical model of the enhanced Tyne Bridge support featuring ledge extensions and wind barriers

Figure 6: BIRD – a kittiwake corridor integrating a riverside walkway for both humans and wildlife, designed by a Northumbria architecture student

The workshop series revealed pronounced shifts in participant perspectives. Close observation and role-reversal exercises catalysed what participants described as “perspective flips”, which moved from anthropocentric defaults. By

the second workshop, discussions had moved beyond notions of simple coexistence to questions of infrastructural adaptation, asking how urban systems might be reconfigured to serve both human and kittiwake needs. In the final session, participants articulated proposals that framed kittiwakes as design collaborators rather than passive subjects of human decision-making, marking the adoption of genuinely interspecies thinking. Looking into these proposals, the concept of “temporal zoning” slowly emerged, as a novel planning strategy that explicitly prioritised avian needs during critical breeding periods like egg laying in May, incubation & hatching between late May and early June, and chick-rearing between June and July (O’Hanlon et al., 2021).

We observed that “ecological empathy” was evident in all three workshops (Figure 7). Many participants advocated seasonal restrictions on building maintenance, construction noise, and recreational activities, reframing urban management as a practice of interspecies time-sharing. Such proposals extend beyond pragmatic adjustments; they signal a profound departure from entrenched human-centred logics toward genuinely multispecies governance. Architects and architectural designers began to integrate seasonal temporalities into their proposals, acknowledging that buildings participate in ecological cycles that exceed human occupancy schedules. Meanwhile, community members shifted their framing of kittiwakes from disruptive outsiders to legitimate urban inhabitants with distinct spatial rights and requirements.

Figure 7: The diagramme synthesises Design Strategies that emerged from ‘Ecological Empathy’

MTHD + Urban Practices

The topics in this brochure can be categorised in multiple ways. In the order that you browse through the book they flow from thinking to doing followed up by some concrete solutions.

FROM THINKING TO DOING

MTHD Basics:

1. **Revitalise urban ecology** – view rooftops and riverfronts as living cliffs.
2. **Take a kittiwake's perspective** – consider their needs for ledges, height, and distance.
3. **Decentre the human** – plan city spaces that give kittiwakes equal claim to nesting areas.
4. **Redefine relationships** – see kittiwakes not as nuisance birds but as fellow urban dwellers.
5. **Focus on the entangled** – map how their nesting connects to fish stocks, river health, and human activity.
6. **Design an intervention** – propose architectural details or artificial ledges that welcome colonies.
7. **Exclude and focus** – limit harmful human access where disturbance threatens chicks.
8. **Address cultural baggage** – challenge perceptions of gulls as pests and share positive narratives

Designing and making:

9. **Ownership over shared ecology** – empower communities to care for kittiwake habitats.
10. **Aesthetically interesting nesting sites** – integrate safe ledges and boxes into the affected construction zone
11. **Noticing entanglements** – highlight how city lighting, noise, and food systems affect birds.
12. **Find affordances** – identify existing balconies, bridge ledges or structures suited for nesting.
13. **Time and temporality** – plan around breeding seasons when disturbance is most risky.
14. **Play** – use playful public art to celebrate the kittiwake presence.
15. **Slow down** – create quiet zones and encourage patient observation of colonies.

A Growing Practice:

16. **Interdisciplinary collaboration** – link the public, ornithologists, ecologists, urban designers, architects, and local councils to ensure everyone participates equally and actively.
17. **Reflective practitioner** – continually learn from bird behaviour and adapt designs.
18. **Embrace complexity, uncertainty and insecurity** – accept that wildlife co-habitation will always involve surprises.
19. **Design the afterlife** – plan for building redevelopment or demolition so kittiwake nesting sites are preserved and continue to thrive.
20. **Empower young citizens** – engage children and youth in monitoring, storytelling, and hands-on projects to nurture long-term care for kittiwake habitats.

Figure 8: From research to practice, the brochure outlines ways of operationalising More-than-Human Design in urban practice.

Workshop documentation revealed critical insights into interspecies design processes that prioritise non-human agency. Direct behavioural observation proved transformative, moving participants beyond anthropocentric assumptions about avian spatial requirements. With the aid of sustained fieldwork, participants developed a sophisticated understanding of kittiwake nesting site criteria, parental care behaviours, and fledgling development patterns, which informed ecologically grounded design decisions rather than human projections of bird needs. Temporal thinking emerged as fundamental, with participants recognising that kittiwake seasonal rhythms and multi-year site fidelity patterns (Harris et al., 2020) must drive architectural interventions, rather than human occupancy schedules determining when ecological considerations might be accommodated. These workshops also demonstrated that accumulated community knowledge about kittiwake behaviour provided essential foundations for genuinely bird-centred design. Local residents possessed a detailed understanding of individual colony dynamics, inter-annual breeding success variations, and population fluctuations, all of which proved invaluable for developing interventions capable of supporting kittiwake flourishing rather than merely tolerating their urban presence. This progression from anthropocentric problem-solving to collaborative multispecies design represents a fundamental paradigm shift in architectural practice, positioning Tyne Kittiwakes not as passive subjects of human design decisions but as active partners in creating shared urban futures that acknowledge legitimate non-human claims to urban territory and temporal priority.

Figure 7 synthesises seven categories of design strategies that emerged from the workshops, ranging from species-specific architectural modifications and regulatory compliance to the breakthrough concept of temporal zoning - seasonal restrictions on human activities that reframe urban management as interspecies time-sharing. The visualisation shows how ecological empathy, operationalised via four core components (behavioural recognition, temporal attunement, spatial perspective-taking, and interspecies interaction), generated concrete design interventions including enhanced bridge supports, modified building facades, and coordinated urban scheduling that prioritises kittiwake reproductive success over human convenience. Building on these strategies, the translation of empirical insights into practical guidance also led to the development of a comprehensive More-than-Human Design (MTHD) brochure specifically tailored for urban kittiwake conservation in cities (Figure 8). The framework synthesises the empirical findings and participant learning into practical suggestions organised across four aspects: foundational principles (based on MTHD Basics), concrete interventions ("Designing and Making"), professional development ("A Growing Practice"), and implementable solutions.

Conclusion

Scaling workshop insights to broader urban transformation confronts systemic obstacles that individual empathy cannot overcome. The proposed "temporal zoning" systems - requiring seasonal restrictions on building maintenance, construction activities, and recreational access - would necessitate fundamental restructuring of urban governance, liability frameworks, and economic models. Current planning legislation, building codes, and professional insurance structures fail to provide the required mechanisms for prioritising non-human needs over human economic interests. The economic implications also remain largely unaddressed in the workshop outcomes. While participants developed compelling spatial interventions, such as enhanced bridge supports and kittiwake-specific building modifications, the research does not offer a framework for determining who bears implementation costs or how market-driven development processes might accommodate ecological requirements that conflict with profit maximisation. The "Kittiwake Hotel" likewise raises unresolved practical challenges: the recently built Saltmeadows tower in Gateshead has failed to attract birds, and the concept entails added maintenance expenses, potential liabilities from bird-related injuries, and possible conflicts with accessibility regulations.

The workshops revealed persistent tensions between different professional epistemologies that remained unresolved. Artists emphasised creative expression and emotional connection with kittiwakes, architects focused on technical feasibility and regulatory compliance, while ornithologists prioritised scientific accuracy in behavioural interpretation. These disciplinary differences suggest that successful interspecies design requires not only interdisciplinary collaboration but also a fundamental restructuring of MTHD professional education and practice paradigms. The temporal constraints of the three-workshop format present another limitation. While participants have shown perspective shifts and developed an "ecological empathy", these attitudinal changes occurred within controlled workshop environments that may not translate to real-world decision-making pressures. The research lacks

longitudinal data on whether participants maintained interspecies thinking when confronting actual development conflicts, budget constraints, or regulatory requirements in their professional practice. Research into the policy mechanisms necessary for institutionalising interspecies design approaches is urgently needed, including investigations of legal frameworks for nonhuman spatial rights, funding models for ecological infrastructure, and regulatory structures capable of balancing competing species claims.

The research also brings forward profound misalignment between MTHD aspirations and current architectural practice structures. While workshops show an appetite for ecologically responsive design, professional education and regulatory environments provide minimal support for interspecies thinking. Transforming architectural practice toward MTHD principles requires systemic changes across educational institutions, professional organisations and policy environments that extend far beyond individual designer intentions. The rising influence of nationalist and anti-environmental political movements has, in recent years, created policy environments increasingly hostile to regulations that might restrict human economic activity in favour of ecological protection (Žuk et al., 2024). Urban planning decisions have become politicised battlegrounds where kittiwake habitat protection could be framed as government overreach rather than evidence-based environmental stewardship. These political dynamics suggest that even technically feasible MTHD approaches may face implementation barriers rooted in ideological resistance to acknowledging nonhuman agency and spatial rights. These workshops, however, suggest that architectural practice might need to fundamentally reconceptualise its role from creating human-serving objects to facilitating interspecies relationships, a shift that challenges core professional identities and economic models. Whether the profession possesses sufficient motivation for such transformation remains an open question that this research cannot answer definitively.

To advance and promote the integration of MTHD in urban practice, this research proposes three core principles for contextually embedded practice, which may inform policymakers and guide future place-making efforts: 1) *Cyclical Responsiveness* requires design interventions that adapt to ecological growth, change, and renewal across multiple temporal scales rather than imposing permanent solutions; 2) *Situated Collaboration* demands emergence from careful attention to existing interspecies relationships within specific localities, requiring what Metcalfe (2015) calls “sensitivity towards nonhuman species” developed via sustained local engagement rather than abstract experimentation; and 3) *Experimental Humility* acknowledges the inherent messiness and unpredictability of ecological systems, embracing Foster and Ervin’s (2020) view of the “inherently intertwined” design-context relationship. These principles distinguish MTHD from other ecological approaches by emphasising process over product, relationship over control, and adaptation over stability, positioning design as the cultivation of interspecies flourishing rather than the management of nonhuman life.

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